

Viruses are microscopic infectious agents composed of genetic material, either DNA or RNA, encased in a protective protein coat. Unlike living organisms, they cannot replicate on their own and must invade the cells of a host—human, animal, plant, or even bacteria—to reproduce. Viruses with RNA as their genetic material can quickly adapt to and exploit these varying conditions because of the high error rates of the virus enzymes (polymerases) that replicate their genomes. It comes as no surprise, then, that several prominent recent examples of emerging or re-emerging diseases are caused by RNA viruses. Influenza, hantaviruses, Ebola virus, and Nipah virus can be included in this list. Moreover, a complex interplay of factors can influence disease emergence. In addition to virus genetic variation (mutation, recombination, and reassortment), environmental factors (including ecological, social, health care, and behavioral influences) can play important roles. These can include (i) changing weather patterns (e.g., El Niño effects) and damming of rivers, which alters potential virus vector or host abundance and distribution, and (ii) tropical deforestation, which brings humans in close contact with these species-rich (hosts and their parasites) environments.

Influenza virus strains that cause worldwide outbreaks (pandemics) are classic examples of emerging viruses that are maintained in other animal hosts before transmission to humans. Influenza viruses are isolated from a variety of animals, including humans, pigs, horses, wild and domestic birds, and even sea mammals. It is a well-established cause of seasonal illness, generally characterized by acute onset of fever, myalgias, and respiratory symptoms. In this case the virus infects the respiratory tract by entering through droplets or contaminated surfaces, targeting epithelial cells in the nose, throat, and lungs. Using its hemagglutinin (HA) protein, the virus attaches to sialic acid receptors on host cells and is taken in via endocytosis. Once inside, the acidic environment triggers the release of the viral RNA (vRNA) into the host cell's nucleus, where it hijacks the host's machinery to replicate and produce viral proteins. Newly formed virus particles are assembled and released by the action of neuraminidase (NA), spreading to nearby cells and causing widespread respiratory damage. Not only that, chronic medical conditions, such as heart disease, lung disease, diabetes, renal disease, rheumatologic disease, dementia, and stroke, can also happen. Regardless of age, those with high-risk conditions have increased rates of

hospitalization and death. Recently, influenza A (H1N1) seems to be the mildest, influenza B is intermediate, and influenza A (H3N2) is most severe, as it has 80% of deaths due to influenza A (H3N2). Regardless of age, those with high-risk conditions have increased rates of hospitalization and death. Thus, high-risk patients aged 45 to 64 years have a risk equivalent to that of all patients aged more than 65 years. Not only that, other groups at risk for influenza complications include those who are pregnant or immunosuppressed. Compared with non-pregnant women, both high and low-risk pregnant women—especially during the third trimester—have more cardiopulmonary events during influenza season.

Ebola virus disease (EVD) is a severe and frequently lethal disease caused by Ebola virus (EBOV). EVD outbreaks typically start from a single case of probable zoonotic transmission, followed by human-to-human transmission via direct contact or contact with infected bodily fluids or contaminated fomites. Most of the cases it targets immune cells like macrophages and dendritic cells. Using its glycoprotein (GP), the virus binds to host cell receptors and enters via macropinocytosis. Once inside, it releases its RNA genome into the cytoplasm, hijacking the host's machinery to replicate and produce viral proteins. The virus disrupts the immune system by impairing dendritic cells and triggering a cytokine storm, leading to severe inflammation and tissue damage. Rapid replication damages blood vessels, causing internal bleeding, organ failure, and widespread systemic infection, while newly formed viruses spread to other cells, exacerbating the disease. A strong risk factor linked to human-to-human EBOV propagation is contact with infected bodily fluids. Indeed, infectious EBOV has been recovered from breast milk, saliva, urine, semen, cerebrospinal fluid, and aqueous humor, in addition to blood and blood derivatives, and detected in amniotic fluid, tears, skin swabs and stool by reverse transcription. Although EBOV RNA has been detected in illness-related bodily fluids (such as diarrhoea and vomitus) infectivity is low. Though the risk factor of Ebola virus (EBOV) infections are unclear, women as caregivers face higher exposure, and EVD incidence peaks at ages 35–44. Children under five have the highest risk of death due to rapid disease progression, though their lower incidence may result from behavioral factors and age-related susceptibility. Pregnant women face high risks of miscarriage, stillbirth, and neonatal death, with EBOV frequently transmitted

transplacentally. EBOV RNA is found in amniotic fluid, placenta, and breast milk, and genetic factors, like specific KIR receptor expressions, may influence fatal outcomes. Emerging RNA viruses, such as influenza and Ebola, highlight the dynamic interplay between viral genetics, host factors, and environmental influences in disease emergence and propagation. Influenza's adaptability and seasonality contrast with Ebola's severe, sporadic outbreaks, emphasizing the diverse challenges these viruses present to global health systems. The disproportionate impact on vulnerable populations, including pregnant women, caregivers, and young children, underscores the need for targeted preventive measures and robust healthcare responses. Enhanced surveillance, vaccination programs, and public health interventions are essential to address the risks posed by these viruses and to prevent future outbreaks.